

Radon-AFMT Invariant Guided Conditional SE-UNet for MRI Tumor Segmentation

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Abstract This paper proposes a brain tumor segmentation method that integrates analytically exact rotation, scale, and translation-invariant (RST-invariant) Radon-AFMT descriptors into a U-Net architecture through Conditional Squeeze-and-Excitation (CSE) blocks. Unlike conventional attention mechanisms based solely on data-driven statistics, the proposed approach conditions channel recalibration on precomputed geometric invariants, enabling geometry-aware feature modulation across encoder stages and the bottleneck. The architecture also includes residual convolutional blocks, attention gates on skip connections, and deep supervision for stable multi-scale training. Experiments on the Figshare Brain Tumor dataset (3,064 MRI images) achieve a Dice score of 0.870, demonstrating the benefit of combining invariant signal representations with deep learning for robust medical image segmentation.

Key words Brain Tumor Segmentation, U-Net, Radon-AFMT Invariants, Squeeze-and-Excitation, Medical Image Segmentation, Deep Learning, MRI..

1 Introduction

Robust image segmentation remains challenging under geometric transformations such as rotation and scale changes. Although convolutional neural networks (CNNs) achieve strong performance, their robustness typically relies on data augmentation rather than explicitly invariant representations.

U-Net and its variants are widely used for segmentation due to their encoder–decoder architecture and skip connections [13]. However, standard CNNs are inherently equivariant only to translations and lack explicit mechanisms for handling rotations and scaling [4], [10]. Attention mechanisms such as squeeze-and-excitation (SE) blocks improve feature representation through channel-wise recalibration [6], but remain purely data-driven.

To address this limitation, we propose a *conditional SE U-Net guided by Radon-AFMT invariants*, where invariant descriptors modulate SE blocks to inject geometric robustness while preserving the expressive power of convolutional features.

The main contributions are: (i) a conditional SE U-Net guided by Radon–AFMT invariants, (ii) a principled integration of invariant descriptors into deep architectures, and (iii) improved segmentation performance on the Figshare brain tumour dataset.

2 Proposed Workflow

This section describes the proposed pipeline, including image pre-processing, the segmentation architecture, Radon-AFMT invariant descriptors, and their integration into a conditional SE-U-Net.

Pre-processing and U-Net architecture. Images from the Figshare Brain Tumour dataset are resized to 256×256 and normalized to $[0, 1]$. Data augmentation includes random rotations ($-20^\circ, 20^\circ$), scaling, flips, cropping, and elastic deformation. Class imbalance between tumour and background is addressed using a combination of Dice and Focal losses with class weighting. Segmentation is performed using a U-Net [13] with an encoder–decoder structure and skip connections. The encoder extracts hierarchical features through convolution and pooling, while the decoder restores spatial resolution via transposed convolutions and feature fusion. A final 1×1 convolution with sigmoid activation produces the tumour segmentation map [8].

Radon-AFMT invariant descriptors. Geometric invariance is achieved using Radon-AFMT descriptors [9,5]. For an image $I(x, y)$, the Radon transform is

$$R_I(r, \theta) = \int I(x, y) \delta(r - x \cos \theta - y \sin \theta) dx dy. \quad (1)$$

The Fourier–Mellin transform in polar coordinates is

$$M_I(k, \nu) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int I(r, \theta) r^{-i\nu} e^{-ik\theta} d\theta \frac{dr}{r}. \quad (2)$$

Introducing $s = \sigma_0 - i\nu$ gives the Radon–AFMT coefficients

$$M_{R_I}(k, s) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int R_I(r, \theta) r^s e^{-ik\theta} d\theta \frac{dr}{r}. \quad (3)$$

Similarity invariants are obtained by normalization

$$\mathcal{I}(k, s) = \frac{M_{R_I}(k, s)[M_{R_I}(1, 1)]^{-k}[M_{R_I}(0, 1)]^{-\frac{s+1}{2}}}{|M_{R_I}(1, 1)|^{-k}}, \quad (4)$$

which ensures invariance to rotation and isotropic scaling.

Proposed Radon-AFMT guided conditional SE-UNet. The proposed architecture extends U-Net by integrating invariant descriptors into channel attention (Fig. 1). Residual convolution blocks improve gradient flow, attention gates [12] refine skip connections, and Conditional Squeeze-and-Excitation (CSE) blocks inject Radon-AFMT invariants into channel-wise attention at each encoder stage and the bottleneck, improving robustness while preserving the encoder–decoder representation (Fig. 2).

Figure 1 – Proposed Radon-AFMT guided SE-UNet architecture.

Figure 2 – Conditional SE block.

3 Experimental Setup

Experiments are conducted on the Figshare Brain Tumour dataset [3], which contains 3,064 MRI images with corresponding binary masks. The dataset includes three tumour types (meningioma, glioma, and pituitary) and presents significant variability in tumour shape, size, and intensity, making it suitable for evaluating segmentation methods.

The proposed model is implemented in PyTorch and trained on a Kaggle P100 GPU using the AdamW optimizer with a learning rate of 4.49×10^{-4} , batch size of 16, and 100 epochs.

Segmentation performance is evaluated using the Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC) and Intersection over Union (IoU). These metrics measure the overlap between the predicted segmentation and the ground-truth mask, where P and G denote the predicted and ground-truth regions. Both metrics range from 0 to 1, with higher values indicating better segmentation performance.

4 Results and Discussion

We evaluate the proposed model in terms of parameter count, quantitative metrics (Dice and IoU), and training behavior.

Table 1 – Model parameter comparison.

Method	Parameters
Proposed method	9,056,272
U-Net	7,851,969
U-Net + SE	7,906,753

Table 1 reports the number of parameters for each model. The proposed architecture slightly increases the parameter count due to the integration of Radon-AFMT invariants and CSE blocks.

Table 2 shows that the proposed model improves over the U-Net baseline and U-Net+SE, achieving a Dice score of 0.870 and IoU of 0.801.

Figure 3 shows a steady decrease of both training and validation losses, indicating stable convergence.

The Dice score progressively increases over epochs, demonstrating improved segmentation performance.

Figure 4 shows qualitative segmentation results, highlighting accurate tumor boundary delineation.

Table 2 – Quantitative comparison.

Method	Dice	IoU
Proposed method	0.870	0.801
U-Net [13]	0.795	0.705
U-Net + SE	0.808	0.718
CRF-TL [1]	0.830	0.840
EAV-UNet [2]	0.768	0.842
CD-SL [15]	0.800	0.907
MST [11]	0.847	0.744
ResUNet101 [7]	0.837	0.850
UNet-ResNet [14]	0.873	0.790

Figure 3 – Training loss and Dice score evolution.

Figure 4 – MRI segmentation results: (a) MRI, (b) ground truth, (c) prediction.

5 Conclusion

This paper introduced the Radon-AFMT Invariant Guided Conditional SE-UNet for brain tumor segmentation from MRI images. By integrating RST-invariant descriptors into the SE block excitation pathway, the model achieves improved channel recalibration based on geometric properties. Experiments on the Figshare Brain Tu-

mor dataset show that the proposed method outperforms the U-Net baseline and SE U-Net, with a Dice coefficient of 0.8686 and IoU of 0.801.

Future work will focus on hyperparameter optimization, exploring alternative fusion strategies, evaluating on multi-modal datasets, and combining the approach with pretrained encoders for further improvements.

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